

Deformed Wing Virus and Varroa Destructor in the Local Honey Bee Colonies *Apis mellifera intermissa* in Algeria

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Abstract : Deformed Wing Virus (DWV) is considered as the most prevalent virus that dangerous the honeybee health worldwide today. In this study we aimed to evaluate the impact of the virus on honeybees (*Apis mellifera intermissa*) mortality in Algeria and we conducted the study on samples collected from the central area in the country. We used PCR for the diagnoses of the (DWV) in the diagnosis. The results had shown a high infestation in the sampled colonies and it represented 42% of the total sample. In this study, we found a clear role of both Varroa destructor mite and DWV on hive mortality in the experimented apiary. Further studies need to be conducted in order to give soled recommendations to the beekeepers, decision makers and stockholders of the Algerian beekeeping sector.

Keywords : honey bee, DWV, Varroa destructor, mortality, prevalence, infestation

Conference Title : ICABBBE 2014 : International Conference on Agricultural, Biotechnology, Biological and Biosystems Engineering

Conference Location : Zurich, Switzerland

Conference Dates : January 14-15, 2014